

Identifying the Level of Teacher's Maturity in the Impactful Gamification Use (IGU) in Abu Dhabi Public Schools

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the maturity level of science and math teachers in Impactful Gamification Use (IGU) in Al Dhafra region public schools in Abu Dhabi. The researcher used concurrent triangulation mixed methodology research design, the research is conducted on a sample selected through a purposive sampling method from the population of public schools' science and math teachers from Al Dhafra region in Abu Dhabi. The results indicate that teachers have a high level of maturity in the impactful use of gamification, Thus, the findings from this research were used to suggest a framework rubric for measuring and improving Impactful Gamification Use (IGU), which can be used by education professionals to achieve better results using educational gamification technologies practically and to enhance the learning of their pupils. The implication of this research is anticipated to be beneficial for teachers, school senior leadership teams, and educational governing bodies to promote and to create a better understanding of how to achieve impactful use of educational gamification technology, and to harness its positive effects on education. The researcher concludes that higher levels of teacher's maturity result in creating and establishing the conditions of the IGU and that using the educational gamification framework rubric can help educators to achieve IGU. Future research can help in testing and improving on the findings of this research and also to apply it to other learning subjects.

Keywords: Gamification, Impactful Gamification Use (IGU), Educational technologies, etc.

Introduction

Gamification is defined as the application of gaming mechanisms to engage users (Cunningham & Zichermann, 2011). Gamification is also characterized by Sailer et al. (2017) as applying gaming techniques and components outside the gaming context. The definition has been extended through the years to include everything that elicits actions, like games in a non-gaming environment that impacts motivation. Gamification, in this research, is defined as applying game design, elements, and characteristics with game mechanics, to non-game educational contexts. Gamification is not a product in its own right; instead, it is the result of educators who incorporate game elements into lessons to change the existing process and how it influences their students and the teaching process. Science and math educators have stated that adding gamification to the learning equation will improve learning outcomes positively and motivate students (Cunningham & Zichermann, 2011). a survey by Vann and Tawfik (2020) argue that participants partake in an activity more fully if it feels exciting and engaging. And to take advantage of this practical aspect, several research studies have explored how Impactful Gamification Use (IGU) leads to improved learning outcomes within education. However, even with all the fancy gamified solutions, the results of implementing gamification in an education context are not that much different from the results gained from implementing other educational technologies, as shown in the work of many researchers, such as Ntokos (2019). he stated that gamification has varying effects on the learning process, and the research by Hanus and Fox (2015), which stated that game mechanics does not lead to improved educational outcomes and instead damage motivation, satisfaction, and empowerment, as an example, he proposed that rewards systems adversely affect motivation. Thus, using gamification without a robust framework that gives teachers a clear road map to achieve impactful use of gamification, and engage students in a way that could lead to the positive improvement on student learning will result in wasting teacher time and resources.

Methodology

The research design used in this research project was the concurrent triangulation design because it is the best method for carrying out research when both quantitative and qualitative data needs to be collected individually but at the same time (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017). Other reasons for using concurrent triangulation design are the limited time for the study, also, both qualitative and quantitative information is important to reach a deep understanding of complex systems such as education, and because the researcher approaches this research with a pragmatic approach based on a pragmatic worldview, with the purpose to overcome the weaknesses of the methods that use one type of data, and to achieve a greater understanding of the subject of the research.

Table 1. Frequency and percentage of response from teachers for scale (IGU E).

Statements of Scale IGU E	Never F (%)	Rarely F (%)	Sometimes F (%)	Often F (%)	Usually F (%)	Always F (%)
How frequently are Points used	3 (3.4)	1 (1.1)	9 (10.1)	14 (15.7)	23 (25.8)	39 (43.8)
How frequently are Badges used	3 (3.4)	5 (5.6)	9 (10.1)	17 (19.1)	33 (37.1)	22 (24.7)
How frequently are Leaderboards used	3 (3.4)	2 (2.2)	12 (13.5)	21 (23.6)	27 (30.3)	24 (27)
How frequently are Performance graphs used	3 (3.4)	4 (4.5)	12 (13.5)	31 (34.8)	20 (22.5)	19 (21.3)
How frequently are Meaningful stories used	8 (9)	6 (6.7)	22 (24.7)	18 (20.2)	24 (27.0)	11 (12.4)
How frequently are Avatars used	7 (7.9)	7 (7.9)	15 (16.9)	21 (23.6)	20 (22.5)	19 (21.3)
How frequently are Teammates used	8 (9)	7 (7.9)	11 (12.4)	23 (25.8)	28 (31.5)	12 (13.5)
How frequently is Competition used	0 (0)	0 (0)	9 (10.1)	18 (20.2)	27 (30.3)	35 (39.3)
How frequently is Progress (feedback)used	0 (0)	2 (2.2)	5 (5.6)	9 (10.1)	25 (28.1)	48 (53.9)

The IGU A scale found that 81 teachers strongly agreed that the gamification tool's elements positively impact student learning, while 84 teachers agreed that they effectively enhance learning. 78 teachers agree that the gamification tool prepares students for 21st-century skills and attitudes, while 83 teachers agree that gamification is easily used within the available tools. The gamification tool's elements are positively affecting teachers' performance and productivity, with 78 teachers strongly agreeing and 80 89.9% agreeing. The gamification tool's elements engage all student types and preferences, with the lowest items focusing on overall performance and productivity.

Table 2. Frequency and percentage of response from teachers for IGU A.

Statements of Scale IGU A	Strongly Disagree F (%)	Disagree F (%)	Neither agree nor Disagree F (%)	Agree F (%)	Strongly agree F (%)
Impact student Learning In a positive way.	3 (3.4%)	1 (1.1%)	4 (4.5%)	31 (34.8%)	50 (56.2%)
Effectively enhance student learning.	4 (4.5%)	1	0 (0%)	45 (50.6%)	39 (43.8%)
Prepare students for 21st-century skills and	4 (4.5%)	1 (1.1%)	6 (6.7%)	32 (36%)	46 (51.7%)

attitudes.					
Used easily by teachers and students within the program procedures and implementation.	3 (3.4%)	1 (1.1%)	2 (2.2%)	49 (55.1%)	34 (38.2%)
Increase the overall performance and productivity of the program.	4 (4.5%)	0 (0%)	7 (7.9%)	37 (41.6%)	41 (46.1%)
Engage students and teachers to adopt the Gamification elements	4 (4.5%)	0 (0%)	5 (5.6%)	43 (48.3%)	37 (41.6%)
Engage all student types and Preferences.	4 (4.5%)	1 (1.1%)	8 (9%)	36 (40.4%)	40 (44.9%)

The IGU Oct scale reveals a significant frequency of occurrences of the Octalysis main drives in the observed lessons. The frequency of occurrences of epic meaning, empowerment, social influence, unpredictability, and avoidance was also found to be high. The IGU Oct scale reveals that teachers using the Octalysis framework often achieve conditions for the framework, with 50% of lessons being to very large extent and 48% being to large extent. The highest frequency of occurrence is found in items two, eight, and nine, which focus on empowerment, ownership, and accomplishment.

Table 3 Frequency and percentage of Lesson observation for (IGU Oct) scale.

Statements of IGU Oct	To a small Extent F (%)	To some Extent F (%)	To a large Extent F (%)	To a very large extent F (%)
Epic Meaning (Emotional entailment)	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (50)	5 (50)
Empowerment	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (10)	9 (90)
Social influence	0 (0)	0 (0)	7 (70)	3 (30)
Unpredictability	0 (0)	1 (10)	7 (70)	2 (20)
Avoidance	0 (0)	0 (0)	7 (70)	3 (30)
Scarcity	0 (0)	0 (0)	8 (80)	1 (10)
Ownership	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (20)	8 (80)
Accomplishment	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (10)	9 (90)

Teachers and students are using educational gamification technology more effectively than before, with a significant increase in frequency and impactful gamification use. The core drive of gamification is evident, driving student empowerment and engagement. The frequency and impact of gamification use are favourable, with teacher

responses favouring an increase in impactful gamification use and improvement. The observer noted regarding impactful gamification use that the gamification tool's unpredictability and scarcity core drives need improvement, while the social influence core drive relies on teacher efforts and creativity. A stable balance between core drives is crucial for impactful gamification use.

Findings

The triangulation of teacher impactful gamification use (IGU) shows a significant positive increase in classroom frequency and impactful use, with most teachers achieving gamification core drives. The positive effect is consistent with frequency increase. The triangulation results show a significant positive increase in teacher classroom frequency of using educational gamification elements, with most teachers achieving the Octalysis framework's core drives. This indicates high teacher maturity in IGU. The gamification tool effectively uses gamification in the classroom to achieve Impactful Gamification Use (IGU) by creating eight motivation core drives. Support and professional development are crucial for teachers' success. Improvement points include collaboration, communication, choice, creativity, and innovation. The gamification tool provided should improve engaging all types of students, especially socializers, and addressing predictability, avoidance, and scarcity. Finally, the final interpretation is that teacher in Abu Dhabi public school who are using gamification tool provided to them by the ministry of education have a high level of maturity in Impactful Gamification Use (IGU).

Conclusions

The Impactful Gamification Use (IGU) conditions in education, particularly in math and science, can be achieved through a balanced approach using educational technology and gamification. The Abu Dhabi public school teachers who are using gamification tool provided to them by the ministry of education are achieving these conditions, with some improvement needed for IGU programs and tools. Improving these conditions will enhance teachers' maturity in using educational gamification, ultimately improving the tools and programs level. Achieving all IGU state conditions practically and systematically requires aligning technology use with certain conditions. The research also shows that higher teacher maturity in IGU could positively impacted student achievement and interest in math and science subjects.

The effect of IGU enhances the learning process. However, further research and analysis of successful programs are needed to develop a more precise framework. The combined flow framework is valuable for education systems and educators worldwide, particularly in the math and science subjects learning environment. Future research should include other learning systems and models to achieve a format that can be used by teachers worldwide with minimal resources and tools.

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